

PRODUCTIVE TIPS FOR IMPROVING THE WRITING SKILL AND COMMON WRITING PROBLEMS

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Abstract: *This article is dedicated to get acquainted with several effective tips for the purpose of improving the writing skill. Additionally, the article concentrates on the importance of writing skill and some challenges that a person can struggle with.*

Key words: *Writing skill, productive ways, practice, research, peer working, editing, challenges, American and British English words.*

Introduction

What is the writing skill itself? What is the most difficult part of the writing process? What are the most productive ways to improve the writing style? What kinds of problems can writers struggle with?

Writing skill is the most significant way of communication and the ability which helps writers to spread their ideas, thoughts as well as messages to a large number of audiences understandably and globally.

Compared to reading, speaking, and listening skills, writing is known as the most challenging skill among them. For the reason, creating an effective piece of writing requires flawless grammar, accuracy, powerful vocabulary, proper pronunciation, organizing progress, and sentence structure.

Why should you improve your writing skill? Considering that, there are several benefits that can be taken by upgrading the writing skill:

- communication with clarity
- making better decisions
- gaining awareness of reality
- learning how to focus more
- dealing with problems.

Additionally, it is a way of strengthening concentration, critical way of thinking, knowledge, creativity, imagination, and self-belief.

Alternatively, no one can be an ideal writer in a day. Since enhancing the writing skill is such a challenge it demands continual practice together with diligence. The most productive tips to improve your writing skill dramatically are:

1. Daily practice. While working on the development of writing skill, practicing everyday is the most significant part of this progress. Choose any theme, write something short, simple, and try to concentrate on it.
2. Always read and research. Continual researching based on enhancing, your writing skill allows you to organize everything thoughtfully and gather a great deal of information on the topic which you are going to write.
3. Peer working and editing. This process is known as the most essential step in writing in order to correct and understand the mistakes which you made and did not pay attention too much.
4. Keep the piece of writing short, simple, clear, and understandable. Try to think about what the readers want to read and use your words or sentences wisely so as to captivate a group of audience.
5. Imitate others' works. Attempt to copy and follow others' writing styles intending to make your writings more better.

Learning how to improve the writing skill is such a challenge that unfortunately there can be some common problems most people usually face while writing. For instance:

- Usage of long and unnecessary sentences
- Repetition of the same words
- Grammatically incorrect forms of sentences
- Mixing to choose correct words. As an example, the table below contains

some samples which commonly lead to several mistakes while picking out.

Affect	Effect
Complement	Compliment
Accept	Except
Title	Entitle
Quite	Quiet
Sometime	Some time
Principal	Principle
Apprise	Appraise

- Not differentiating American and British English words.

-re vs. -er	-ll vs. -l	-our vs. -or	-ise vs. -ize
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British English: centre	British English: travelled	British English: colour	British English: organize
American English: center	American English: traveled	American English: color	American English: organize

Conclusion

To sum up the ideas which are mentioned above, enhancing the writing skill is the most challenging and long-term progress. Moreover, this process contains concentration, brainstorming, planning, first draft, editing, reorganizing, adding details, and final steps. The daily practice and understanding your mistakes by correcting them are the main factors to manifest success in your writings.

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